

Analytical Applications of 2-Propionyl-1-Naphthol Oxime (2-PRONAPOX). Part-IV : Gravimetric Determination of Manganese[†]

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Manuscript received 29 July 1976, revised 27 June 1978, accepted 31 August 1978

2-PRONAPOX forms with Mn^{2+} a dark green *bis* chelate $Mn(C_{13}H_{12}O_2N)_2$ precipitated quantitatively from aqueous solutions at pH 8-8.5, soluble in dioxane, but sparingly soluble in ethanol, chloroform, ether, acetone and benzene and stable to heat up to 140°. Mn^{2+} has been determined gravimetrically in amounts from 11 to 31 mg, the average error being $\pm 0.04\%$ and maximum error 0.17%. Determination of Mn^{2+} in binary mixtures containing moderate amounts of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} or Zn^{2+} has been found to be satisfactory. Interference due to various cations and anions has been studied. $P_2O_7^{3-}$ and MnO_4^- amongst anions and Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Pb^{2+} and Hg^{2+} interfere seriously. The authors find that 2-PRONAPOX affords a simple, quick and accurate method for gravimetric determination of Mn^{2+} under conditions stated.

REACTIONS of 2-PRONAPOX with metal ions and its applications to the gravimetric determination of Cu^{2+} and Pd^{2+} have been reported by Merchant *et al.*^{1,2,3}. It was found by them that Mn^{2+} forms a dark green precipitate with 2-PRONAPOX in neutral and alkaline medium. In the present work this reaction has been investigated systematically and a gravimetric method for determination of Mn^{2+} with 2-PRONAPOX has been developed.

Experimental

A. R. $MnSO_4$ (Crystalline) after dehydration was used and a solution containing about 1 mg per ml. was standardised by the pyrophosphate method⁴. All other chemicals used were A. R. grade. 2-PRONAPOX was prepared by the method described by Tambat and Merchant¹. An Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Results

Determination of Mn^{2+} :

Precipitation of Mn^{2+} complex starts at pH 5.7 and is complete in the pH range 8.0-8.5. The dark

green Mn^{2+} *bis* chelate is soluble in dioxane, sparingly soluble in C_2H_5OH , $CHCl_3$, $(C_2H_5)_2O$, $(CH_3)_2CO$ and benzene. It is stable to heat up to 140°. Analysis of the *bis* chelate, $Mn(C_{13}H_{12}O_2N)_2$ (Found: Mn, 11.32%, C, 64.10%, H, 4.7%, N, 5.82%; Requires: Mn, 11.38%; C, 64.63%, H, 4.97%; N, 5.80%).

Procedure :

To an aliquot of Mn^{2+} solution containing between 5 and 31 mg of the metal in about 200 ml solution, a 15% excess (over calculated) of the reagent (using a 1% ethanolic solution) is added and pH adjusted to 8.0-8.5 with dilute NaOH solution. The dark-green precipitate obtained is digested on a waterbath for 20 to 30 min. at about 60°, filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G_3 or G_4), washed with 50% ethanol till free from excess reagent (tested with a drop of conc. HNO_3 till no violet coloration) and the precipitate is dried at 105-110° to a constant weight. Mn^{2+} is weighed as $Mn(C_{13}H_{12}O_2N)_2$. Conversion factor for Mn^{2+} is 0.1138.

Interference studies :

Interference due to various anions and cations was studied. The results are given in Table 1.

[†]Presented at the 6th Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, Ahmedabad, November, 1968.

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TABLE—1. INTERFERENCE DUE TO FOREIGN IONS

Cations Ion added	Tolerance limit* mg.	Masking agent used	Anions Ion added	Tolerance limit* mg.
Li ⁺ , Be ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Mg ²⁺ Cr ³⁺ , Zn ²⁺	200		F ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ CO ₃ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ , MoO ₄ ²⁻ , acetate	1000
Fe ³⁺	45.8	Citrate	I ⁻	256
Co ²⁺	42.00	NH ₄ CNS	SO ₃ ²⁻	520
UO ₂ ²⁺	96.4 (U)	Na ₂ CO ₃	PO ₄ ³⁻	255
Pb ²⁺	55.5	Tartrate	P ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	36.4
Cd ²⁺	152.8	KI	CNS ⁻	840
Bi ³⁺	184.2	Tartrate	CN ⁻	450
Sn ²⁺	96.6	"	ClO ₄ ⁻	256
Ag ⁺	88.0	NaCN	VO ₃ ⁻	385
Au ³⁺	45.5	"	WO ₄ ²⁻	524
Hg ²⁺	64.2	"	MnO ₄ ⁻	10
			citrate	500
			tartrate	200
			borate	360

*Limiting amount of foreign ion in presence of which Mn²⁺ can be determined with an accuracy of 16.49±0.04 mg.

Separation of Mn²⁺ from Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ :

As Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ are precipitated by the reagent at pH 1, 2.5 and 5 respectively¹ studies on separation of Mn²⁺ from these ions from binary mixtures were carried out. From mixtures containing known amounts of Mn²⁺ and one of the above cations, the latter was first precipitated with 2-PRONAPOX at pH values stated above and determined using procedures described earlier. Mn²⁺ was then determined in the filtrate after addition of more reagent and raising the pH to 8.0-8.5.

As Zn²⁺ does not give any precipitate or coloration with 2-PRONAPOX, determination of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ in binary mixtures was studied using 2-PRONAPOX for separation and determination of Mn²⁺. From a mixture of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺ was precipitated with 2-PRONAPOX (pH 8.0-8.5) keeping Zn²⁺ in solution at this pH by addition of NH₄Cl. Zn²⁺ was determined in the filtrate by the pyrophosphate method. It was found that NH₄⁺ salts like NH₄Cl, NH₄NO₃ and (NH₄)₂SO₄ have no effect on the precipitation of Mn²⁺ with 2-PRONAPOX.

Discussion

It has been found that the most suitable range of concentration of Mn²⁺ for determination is 11-31 mg, the maximum error being 0.17%. Determination of Mn²⁺ in amounts below and above this range involves greater error. The procedure determination of Mn²⁺ is quick and simple.

P₂O₇²⁻ and MnO₄⁻ interfere seriously. I⁻, PO₄³⁻, ClO₄⁻, tartrate, borate, and VO₃⁻ do not interfere up to moderate concentrations, F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, CO₃²⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, SO₃²⁻, CNS⁻, MoO₄²⁻ and acetate do not interfere.

Amongst cations Fe³⁺, Co²⁺, Au³⁺, Pb²⁺ and Hg²⁺ interfere seriously. Li⁺, Mg²⁺, Be²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺ and Zn²⁺ do not interfere.

Results of the separations show that separation and determination of Mn²⁺ and Pd²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺ and Ni²⁺ are quite satisfactory. 2-PRONAPOX affords a simple and accurate method for separation and determination of Mn²⁺ in binary mixture with Zn²⁺, the error being 0.1% even for amounts of Zn²⁺ in tenfold excess over Mn²⁺.

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to express their thanks to Shri. R. S. Kulkarni for microanalysis of Mn²⁺ complex.

References

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